

Land Grabbing Threatens Tenure Security And Sustainable Development In Oyo State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined land grabbing including “Omo Onile” phenomenon, Farmers – Fulani conflicts, acquisitions and Encroachment activities and their impacts on land tenure security and sustainable development in Oyo State. Structured interview guide were prepared and served on market men and women (Farmers, Traders and Artisans) who reside in the peri-urban area of Ibadan region and Oke-Ogun/Ibarapa area in Oyo State and who were affected by land grabbing activities. One major market in each peri-urban local governments in Ibadan region was selected and three popular markets known for Oke-Ogun people were strategically chosen within Ibadan city where trader and farmers from Oke-Ogun were met and interviewed. 137 structured interviews were purposively administered on them. Data collected include their land ownership rights, the various forms of land grabbing, expropriation and encroachment in the area and dimensions of land tenure security of people affected. One hypothesis was formulated and tested with inferential statistical method (spearman Rank correlation co-efficient) at 0.05 level of significance. Others were analyzed with descriptive statistics (Frequency and percentage) the results revealed that land grabbing activities affect the dimensions of tenure security of people sustainable development and livelihood of the communities in the area. Therefore it is recommended that land grabbed Fraudently, forcefully and illegally should be redeemed and re-allocated to the owner and culprit punished and prosecuted to serve as deterrent to others. Also those who suffered tenure insecurity as a result of government acquisition should be adequately compensated. Lastly, public awareness should be intensified on the importance of acquisition for public purpose.

KEYWORDS: Land grabbing, tenure security, sustainable development.

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INTRODUCTION

Land grabbing has become a serious global problem. This practice involves unlawful appropriation of land for various purposes including large scale bio-fuel and agricultural projects which significantly undermine tenure security by dispossessing individuals and community members of their lands and creating widespread uncertainty about land ownership (Titilope Joseph 2024). It manifest in different forms globally. For instance land may be grabbed from the community by the government to foreign investors (Morges 2010, Sanni Umar Ibrahim 2025, Kuruki & Ngetich 2017, Tan-Ngugen 2010). For instance the government of Kenya embarked on public-private partnership (PPP) with foreign investors and grabbed land for agricultural concession (Kuruki & Ngerich 2017) Galula Lulalu food security project covers about 1.2million Acres grabbed from various communities where Kenya government provided land and related infrastructure while foreign investors set up factories to process the produce in the guest to meet the global demand for food security (Kuruki & Ngetich 2017). There is also a diversion of the grabbed land to produce bio-fuel crops to meet the aggressive global energy demand. For instance in Tana river Delta area in Kenya Bedford bio-fuel a Canadian incorporated multi-national company has acquired 160,000 hectares for cultivating Jetropha Curcas (Kuruki & Ngetich 2017). According to him this land is used for the production of energy sources which consequently put the tenure security of individual and communities in Kenya at risk. Similar form of land grabbing occurred in Nigeria. For instance GNAL (Great Northern Agricultural Ltd) a Chinese owned company acquired 12,000 hectares of land including farmlands and residential areas of many villages in Jigawa State for Agricultural purpose which negatively affected tenure security and source of sustenance of the community members (Sanni Umar Ibrahim 2025) closely related to this form of land grabbing is illegal occupation and encroachment on individual land by the so-called (omo-onile) sons of original land owners. These groups of people forcefully take possession of land by the use of thugs and

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fake court judgments. This land may be resold to the owner or another person if the owner has no money to redeem the land. This practice also threatens the tenure security, livelihood of the owner and property market (Odufa et al 2023). This category of land grabbing is illegal occupation and encroachment on individuals land which often resulted to litigation and threatens tenure security of the rightful owner and delay development. Evidence of existence of this form of land grabbing in Oyo State occurred at Asaaju village, Jenriyin Area, Lagelu Local Government Area where police and court officials supervised demolition of illegal structures put on the grabbed land in suit No 1/855/2012 (Samuel Anyanwu 2024). Another is Rural land Grabbing and farmer-harder conflict in iwajowa Local Government Area. (Christiana U. 2021) iwofun where individuals alleged that thugs are used to disposses farmers of their lands. The last category is acquisition of land for government projects. Section 44 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and Section 29(1) of the Land Use Act of 1978 provide that if a right of occupancy is revoked for overriding public interest the holder or occupier shall be entitled to compensation for the value at the date of revocation of the unexhausted improvement.

However, where the acquiring authority fails to do this, it put the individual and affected communities at risk of tenure security and sustainable livelihood (Orkorji Uthey 2019). Area where land right is not registered or area with weak tenure security is usually a target by the acquiring authority for land grabbing (Kruki & Ngetich 2017 Regassa et al 2018). For instance unregistered land title is susceptible to vertical land pressure where the more powerful actor seeking land could be an invading Army or the State when politically motivated could take such land away through the threat of violence or power of eminent domain, (Holland & Diop 2022, Punch 2025) and thereby put the original owners at difficult situations which could negatively affect their tenure security and only means of sustenance (Sanni Umar Ibrahim 2025).

The global response to land grabbing which brings about tenure insecurity include Sustainable Development Goals (SDGS) with an ambition to end poverty in all forms and seek to end malnutrition and achieve food security and sustainable development. Both goals emphasize resilience for vulnerable populations. Also UN indicator 1.4.2 in SDGs is meant to monitor the security of land tenure and property rights by country during sustainable development goals until 2030 (Rick De Satge 2022). In addition to these, frameworks are put in place to assist land governance in order to ensure land tenure security. These Include the New Urban Agenda (NUA), the voluntary guidelines on responsible governance of tenure of land, fisheries and Forest in Africa and guiding principles on large scale Land-Based investment in Africa (UN-Habitat 2017).

In Nigeria different policies and programmes have been adopted to protect the land rights of the people for instance, the Presidential Technical Committee on land reform adopted systematic land titling and registration approach and selected Kano and Ondo States for the pilot survey (PTCLR 2016) Likewise some states such as Lagos, Oyo, Ekiti and Ogun have set up different Anti-Land grabbing laws and task force in order to eliminate all forms of land grabbing activities. Recently Oyo State has devised means of regularizing informal land rights of people through Certificate of Occupancy redefined measure to increase market fluidity to remove information asymmetry which hinders transactions in land. (Olukotun 2022).

Despite all these, it was estimated that about 70% of the people globally and in developing countries in particular still do not have any form of land tenure security on the land they use, occupy and depend on for individual livelihood and community stability (UN – Habitat 2017, FAO 2026).

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The research aim is to assess the impact of land grabbing on land tenure security and sustainable development in Oyo State. The Objectives are to :

- i) Investigate Land ownership right of people in the study area
- ii) Investigate the various forms of land grabbing in the study area.
- iii) Investigate the various dimensions of land tenure security of people affected by land grabbing activities.
- iv) Proffer suggestions to the individuals and government on how to increase tenure security of the people and enhance sustainable development.

Hypothesis:

Ho: Land grabbing activities have no significant impact in security of tenure and sustainable development in the study area.

H: Land grabbing activities have significant impact on security of tenure and sustainable development in the study area.

JUSTIFICATION FOR THE STUDY:

Land tenure is necessary for a fluid market in land (Olukotun 2022)

If land owners have insecure claims to their lands they will have difficulty transferring such land in a legally accepted way to the willing buyers. Also it will inhibit the operation of the credit market. This is because without marketable registered title, institutional lenders are not inclined to accept the land as a mortgage guarantee. The study is also justified by the fact that over 70% of land owners globally and in developing countries in particular lacks secured tenure to their land (UN- Habitat 2017, FAO 2026)

Convincing empirical studies have been conducted on land grabbing and effect on sustainable development, property market among others. For instance Sani Umar Ibrahim 2025, Odufa et al 2023, Morges 2010, Tan-Nguyen 2010, Alabi 2021, the World Bank

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2010, Edohen & Eghareuba 2025 among others. However, despite this mounting volume of empirical studies on various aspect of land grabbing, land right and effect on sustainable development in different regions of the world, gaps for further studies remains wide. There are very few studies and documentations on the impact of land grabbing on land tenure security and rigorous empirical evidence to support this crucial link is thin and mixed. There is a dearth of evidence particularly in Oyo State to support the assertion that land grabbing negatively affect land tenure security and sustainable development. It is therefore envisaged that this literature gap will be filled by using empirical findings from this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Land

Land is a multifaceted concept defining the solid, terrestrial surface of the earth, extending to the soil, subsoil, natural resources and legally to any permanent attachment like building (James Chen 2025). It encompasses all physical elements, bestowed by nature on a specific area or piece of property, the environment, fields, for just minerals, animals and bodies of water. Legally and economically a piece of land is a factor in some form of production.

Land Tenure

Land tenure has succenently been defined as the term and condition in which land is held, used and trasacted. (Adam et al 1999). It is in the relationship whether legally or customarily defined among people as individual or groups with respect to land (FAO 2002). The legal approach recognizes the dejure (formal, statutory) i.e how the land is held and associated rights which include right to assign, transfer possession right to lease, right to occupy, right to bequeath, right of base on natural love and affection among others. The customary land tenure approach is the system of land holding indigenous to Nigerians (Arko et al 2019). The evolution of this system and the various principles regarding same exhibit the historical credentials rooted in the custom and tradition of the different ethno-cultural groupings in Nigeria over a period of time (Smith 1999).

Concept of Tenure security

Tenure security is defined as the landholders's perception that his right will be upheld by the individual, state and the society at large (Dachanga et al 2021). Security or tenure has been measured in the literature in different ways (Griffit0Charles 2004). It is indirectly measured through the use of documentation intensity of land use and tenure type. Security of tenure exists in three dimensions the depth of security of tenure or assurance, the breadth of the security of tenure which relates to the range of supported use to which land can be put. The third dimension is the duration of the security of tenure which results to the length of time for which the right may be held from month to month for tenancy to leasehold interest

Concept of land grabbing/expropretion

This is an unlawful appropriation of land for various purposes (Titilope Joseph 2024). Land may be grabbed by the government to foreign investors (Kruike & Ngeteh 2017). Land may be grabbed by omo-onile fraudulently. This is illegal means of getting land from rightful owner. It is also used when government take land for public interest and fails to adequately compensate the rightful owner (Okorji Uthey 2019).

Sustainable Development

From the standpoint of the proactive approach the whole world is exploring the concept of sustainable development as an approach that will permit continued improvement in the present quality of life at a lower intensity of resources use, leaving behind for future generation an undiminished or even enhanced stock of natural resources and other assets (Brundtland 1987). It is defined as the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland 1987).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY/MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Study Area is Oyo State. However, Ibadan region and Oke-Ogun/Ibarapa area were purposively selected for this study because of the occurrence of land grabbing, acquisition in the area. The peri-urban area of Ibadan region which consist of Akinyele, Ido, Lagelu, Egbeda, Oluyole and Ona-Ara together with Iwajowa local government in Oke-Ogun were considered for the study. These area is less developed and predominantly used for Agricultural purposes. The price of land is lower than the inner city of Ibadan region. Consequently, it attracts the lower and middle class people who rush for the place to embark on agricultural practice and incremental housing development (Alabi 2021)

MAP OF THE STUDY AREA

Source: <http://www.google.com/src?map-of-Ibadan.html> map of the study area 2022.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

In order to achieve the research objectives a survey research design was adopted. Qualitative method was adopted for the study to elicit primary data about the respondent's perceptions on land ownership pattern, land grabbing and dimension of their land tenure security affected as a result of land grabbing activities. Interview method and Focus group discussion were used for data collection. These methods are appropriate for the study according to Kumar 2005 and Creswell 2014.

Sampling techniques and sample sizes:

Stratified and purposive sampling was adopted for the study. For the purpose of easy data collection and ensure representative sample, the sample frame (Oyo State) was divided based on existing markets where the affected respondents were easily contacted. This study made use of one (1) popular market in each of the local governments in the peri-urban of Ibadan region and three (3) markets in Ibadan that are popularly known for Oke-Ogun farmers and traders where they sell their agricultural products in Ibadan city. The reason is to access the land owners who are farmers and traders who have been involved in one form of land grabbing or the other on market days and have consequently suffered from land tenure insecurity in their respective areas. 18 questionnaires were administered in each local government in the peri-urban of Ibadan region while 42 questionnaires were administered on the market traders and farmers in the chosen popular market that are known for Oke-Ogun traders within Ibadan where their farm products are bought and sold. The administered questionnaires were aided with Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with the help of two (2) research assistants to enhance understanding. The questionnaire administration technique is as shown in the table below:

Table 2 Questionnaires Administration Techniques and Response:

S/N	LGA	Selected Markets	No of Questionnaires Administered	No of Questionnaires Retrieved
1	Akinyele	Ojoo	18	18
2	Ido	Akufo	18	18
3	Egbeda	Egbeda	18	15
4	Ona-Ara	Akanran	18	14
5	Lagelu	Olodo	18	16
6	Oluyole	Orisunbare	18	14
7	Chosen popular markets in Ibadan for Oke-Ogun Farmers and Transfers	Bodija Sango Oja-oba	22 20	22 20
		Total	150	137

Source Field Survey 2026

Structured questionnaire were used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, section A deals with Demographic characteristics of the respondents; Gender, Marital Status, Age, Education, Income and Occupation, while Section B deals with property ownership pattern, perceived purpose of land grabbing and perceived dimensions of land tenure security effected. 150 copies of the questionnaires were administered (Table 2) but after screening 13 copies were found not usable for analysis. Thus the study was based on 137 usable questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analyzed with both descriptive frequency and percentage bar chart and inferential statistics (Spear man rank correlation co-efficient and student 't') were used for the set hypothesis.

RESULTS

PART (A) Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by Gender, Marital Status, Age, Education, Income and Occupation

S.N	Variable	Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender (a) Male (b) Female	52 85	37.95 62.04
2.	Marital Status (a) Single (b) Married (c) Divorced (d) Widow/ widower	20 84 33	15 61.3 24
3.	Age group (a) 21-30yrs (b) 31-40yrs (c) 41-50yrs (d) 50yrs & above	2 20 85 20	1.5 21.9 62 15
4.	Education (a) No Formal Education (b) SSCE/WAEC (c) ND/NCE/HND/First Degree (d) Above First Degree	90 42 5	65.7 30.7 3.6
5.	Income (a) Below ₦ 70,000/month (b) ₦ 70,000 / month (c) ₦ 71,000/ month (d) ₦ 81,000& Above /month	28 68 41	20.4 50 30
6.	Occupation (a) Farming (b) Trading/Artisan (c) Civil servant (d) Retiree/Unemployed	30 90 Nil 17	21.9 65.7 12.42

Source: Field Survey 2026

Table 3: provides information on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondent. The table presents the frequency and percentage of respondent for each category of the variable. The first variable presented is gender, which shows that 85 (62.04) of the respondents were female and 52 (37.95) were male. The female majority would be because of the place (markets) where the sample was drawn which mainly consist of markets women traders. The second variable is marital status which indicates that the majority of the respondents 61.3% were married followed by widow/widower 24% and single 15%. The third variable is age group which shows that the largest group of respondents 62% were in the age range of 41-50 years followed by 31-40yrs 21.9%, 50 years and above 15% and 21-30 years 1.5%. The fourth variable presented is education qualification which indicate that 65.7% of the respondents had SSCE/WAEC followed by ND/NCE/HND/ first degree (30.7%). Above first degree 3.6% the fifth variable is income which shows that the majority respondents 50% had an income range of N71,000 - N80,000 per month followed by N81,000 and above (30%) N70,000 per month (28%) and the least in below N70,000 per month (0%). The final variable presented it occupation of the respondent. The majority are traders and Artisans (65.7). This may be because of the area (markets) where sample was drawn. Followed by farming () retiree/unemployed (21.9%). None of the respondents is a civil servant and the least is the retiree/unemployed which is 12.4%.

Part B: Property Ownership Pattern.

Showing year of occupation means of acquisition, title held development on site, type of land grabbing experienced and dimension of tenure security affected.

(1) **TABLE 4: Showing length of years of occupation.**

		Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
(a)	Less than 10yrs	14	10.2
(b)	11- 20yrs	8	5.8
(c)	21-30yrs	20	14.9
(d)	31- 40yrs	81	59.1
(e)	40yrs & Above	14	10.2

Source: Field Survey 2026

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TABLE 4: shows the length of years of occupation by the respondent. Majority of the respondents had acquired their land (59.1%). Between 31- 40 years ago. This is followed by 21-30 years which accounts for (14.9%) of the respondents. Followed by 40 years and above which represent (10.2%) and less than 10yrs (10.2%). while the length in between 11- 20yrs (5.8%).

(2) **TABLE 5: Showing means of acquisition**

		Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
(a)	By gift		
(b)	By inheritance	52	38
(c)	By purchase	85	62.0
(d)	Others (specify)		

Source: Field Survey 2026

TABLE 5: showing the means of acquisition by the respondent. The majority of the respondent acquired the land by purchase (62%) this is followed by inheritance from their forefathers (38%). No acquisition was made by gift on the basis in natural here and affection.

(3) **TABLE 6: Showing Title held**

		Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
(a)	Land Agreement	45	32.8
(b)	Record copy survey	30	21.9
(c)	Registered COF	10	7.3
(d)	No title (family land)	52	38

Source: Field Survey 2026

TABLE 6: showing the title held by the Respondent on their land. Table 6 above reveals that 38% of the respondent has no registered title to the land, being family land inherited from their forefathers this is followed by land agreement which represent 32.8%, followed by 21.9% for those with record copy survey and the least in those with registered Certificate of Occupancy (CoF) which is 7.3.

(4) **TABLE 7: Showing development on site**

		Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
(a)	Agricultural/Farming	80	58.4
(b)	Commercial/industrial	27	19.7
(c)	Residential	30	21.9
(d)	Others (specify)		

Source: Field Survey 2026

TABLE 7: Shows the development on site. This table reveals that 58.4% of the respondent practice agriculture and farming on their land. This is focused by those who have varying stages of completed residential buildings 21.9% followed by those with light industries and commercial properties. (19.7%)

(5) **TABLE 8: Type of land grabbing experienced**

		Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
(a)	Taking land from individual & community for the use of foreign investors	2	1.46
(b)	Illegal expropriation and encroachment by individual	48	35
(d)	Encroachment on government acquired land by individuals	11	8
(e)	Acquisition for government projects	76	55.5

Source: Field Survey 2026

TABLE 8: Reveals the varying type of land grabbing activities experienced by the respondent. The table shows that acquisition for government project without adequate compensation for the acquired property is the highest form of land grabbing experienced (55.5%) (Okorgi Ukachau 2019) this is followed by illegal encroachment by the individuals including "Omo onile phenomenon" which represent 35% of the respondents (Odun fa et al 2023). Encroachment by the individual on government acquired land who refused to go after represent 8% (Obueze H.U et al 2021) and the last represent those whose land was revoked by the government

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for the use of foreign investors; (Obueze H.U 2023) this represent 1.46% of the respondents. (Sunni Umar Ibrahim 2025, Kuruiki and Ngetich 2017)

(6) **TABLE 9: Dimensions of security of tenure softened by land grabbing activities**

		Frequency (freq)	Percentage (%)
(a)	Ownership right recognition by individual, state & society at large	4	2.9
(b)	Use right including right of occupation, sale transfer of right, inheritance etc	63	45.3
(c)	Right to enjoy the land for a reasonable length of time from month, year to year and a leasehold of 99 years	21	15.3
(d)	Right to the process and compensation	50	36.6

Source: Field Survey 2026

TABLE 9: Show the varying dimensions of tenure security affected by land grabbing activities. From the table, it is evident that, the use right of the people was affected, this include occupation right, sale, transfer of possession and inheritance rights among others, this represent 45.3%. This is followed by right to due process and compensation. The right of people to due process and adequate compensation was also affected. These categories of people were not adequately compensated for the land expropriated by the government and consequently it affects their livelihood and possibility for inheritance by the children of the owner. This represents 36.5% of the respondents. This is followed by those whose right was cut short off by the grabbing activities. These are the category of people who are on leasehold interest of year to year up to a leasehold of 99 years. These represent 15.3% of the respondents. Lastly are those ownership right were affected as a result of the grabbed land. Their ownership right was no longer recognized by the community, the state and the society at large after the land has been taken away from them. This represents 2.9% of the respondents.

HYPOTHESIS: Spearman Rank correlation coefficient was used to test the formulated hypothesis (Appendix 1). The result of this test shows that there is a strong positive correlation of 0.9 between land grabbing activities and security of tenure of the affected people. This implies that when the land grabbing activities increase land tenure insecurity of the people and community increase as well. (Appendix 1)

DISCUSSION

Table 8 shows that acquisition for government projects without adequate compensation affected the livelihood and sustainable development of the affected people and the community at large. This finding is in line with observation of Okoji Utchay (2019) who evaluated concept of adequate compensation by conduction an analysis of case lands from high courts. Encroachment on government acquired land is also a source of problem (Obueze.H.U et al 2021). These category of people refused to leave their land acquired for public use Land grabbing for investors is insignificant as shown in table 8.

Table 9 Show the various dimensions of security of tenure affected by the land grabbing activities. The table shows that every dimension of tenures security was affected including occupation and use right, transfer right, inheritance right among others which consequently affected the livelihood and sustainable development of the people in the area, this findings is in tandem with Noah, Echa Altah (2014) , Godwin Uyi Ojo & Raphael Ayama Offiong (2018). Taiwo Oladapo Babalola (2022). World Bank Zoomer.A (2010). Sanni Umar Ibrahim (2025).

CONCLUSION

Based on the above findings it is concluded that all forms of land grabbing activities negatively affect security of tenure, the livelihood and sustainable development of the land owner and communities concerned in the study area (appendix 1). The following recommendations are suggested:

- (1) It is recommended that those whose property was revoked for public interest should be adequately compensated without delay.
- (2) Land grabbed fraudulently should be reallocated back to the owner and the culprit should be prosecuted to serve as deterrent to others.
- (3) If land is to be grabbed for foreign investment purpose, the indigenous land owner's security of tenure livelihood and sustenance should be considered and take care of by the government.
- (4) The law against land grabbing in Oyo State should be strictly enforced.

APPENDIX 1

Data:

SN	X	Y	X ^r	Y ^r	D	D ²
1.	2	4	1	1	0	0
2.	48	63	3	4	-1	1
3.	11	21	2	3	0	0
4.	72	50	4	3	1	1
						Σd ^e -2

Finding correlation coefficient between x and y using Spearman Rank Formula

$$\text{Formula} - 1-6\left[\frac{\sum d^2}{n(n^2-1)}\right]$$

$$1-6\left[\frac{1}{4(16-1)}\right]$$

$$1-6\left[\frac{1}{4(15)}\right]$$

$$1-6\left[\frac{1}{60}\right]$$

$$1-6[0.0167]$$

$$1-0.1=0.9$$

$$r = 0.9$$

There is positive association (0.9) between land grabbing activities and dimensions of security of tenure suffered by the affected people.

In order to check whether this result happened by chance or not, we used student 't'

Ho: It happened by chance

H1: It happened not by chance

$$t = r \frac{\sqrt{N-2}}{1-r^2}$$

$$t = 0.9 \frac{\sqrt{4-2}}{1-0.81}$$

$$t = 0.9 \frac{\sqrt{2}}{1-0.81}$$

$$t = 0.9 \frac{1.414}{1-0.81}$$

$$t = 0.9 \frac{1.414}{0.19}$$

$$t = 0.9 (7.44)$$

$$t - \text{calculated} = 6.7$$

$$t - \text{critical value} = 2.365$$

$$t\text{-cal } 6.7 > t\text{-critical } 2.365$$

Therefore Ho is rejected

and Hi is accepted.

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